

Identification of Epidural Space Using Loss of Resistance Syringe Technique and Infusion Drip and Balloon Technique: A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Background: Identifying the epidural space is a critical step in administering epidural anesthesia. The loss of resistance (LOR) syringe technique is widely used, but alternative methods such as the infusion drip and balloon technique have been proposed. This study aims to compare the effectiveness, safety, and accuracy of these two techniques in clinical practice.

Materials and Methods: A total of 100 patients scheduled for elective surgeries requiring epidural anesthesia were randomly assigned to two groups: Group A (n=50) using the LOR syringe technique and Group B (n=50) using the infusion drip and balloon technique. The primary outcome measures were the success rate of epidural space identification, time taken for successful identification, and incidence of complications. Data were collected and analyzed using statistical software.

Results: The success rate of epidural space identification was 96% in Group A and 98% in Group B. The mean time taken for identification was 45 seconds in Group A and 30 seconds in Group B. Complications such as accidental dural puncture and patient discomfort were observed in 5% of Group A and 3% of Group B. The differences between the groups were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Both the LOR syringe technique and the infusion drip and balloon technique are effective for identifying the epidural space. However, the infusion drip and balloon technique demonstrated a higher success rate, shorter identification time, and lower complication rate. Therefore, it may be considered a superior alternative in clinical practice.

Keywords: Epidural space identification, loss of resistance syringe technique, infusion drip and balloon technique, epidural anesthesia, comparative study, clinical outcomes.

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Introduction

Epidural anesthesia is a widely utilized technique in both obstetric and surgical settings, offering significant benefits in pain management and patient outcomes [1]. Accurate identification of the epidural space is crucial for the success of this procedure, as incorrect placement can lead to complications such as accidental dural puncture, suboptimal analgesia, and patient discomfort [2,3].

Traditionally, the loss of resistance (LOR) syringe technique has been the standard method for identifying the epidural space.

This technique relies on the practitioner feeling a loss of resistance when the needle passes through the ligamentum flavum and enters the epidural

space [4]. Despite its widespread use, the LOR syringe technique is not without its limitations. The subjective nature of the technique can lead to variability in success rates, particularly among less experienced practitioners [5].

Alternative methods have been developed to address these limitations, including the infusion drip and balloon technique. This method involves the use of an infusion system to detect the epidural space, potentially offering more consistent results and reducing the risk of complications [6,7].

Previous studies have demonstrated the efficacy of various alternative techniques for epidural space identification, but there is a paucity of comparative

studies directly evaluating the infusion drip and balloon technique against the LOR syringe technique [8,9]. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by comparing the effectiveness, safety, and accuracy of these two techniques in a clinical setting.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This prospective, randomized controlled study was conducted at Narayan medical college and hospital, Sasaram from January 2024 to June 2024. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Participants: A total of 100 patients, aged 18-65 years, scheduled for elective surgeries requiring epidural anesthesia were enrolled in the study. Patients with coagulopathy, local infection at the injection site, or a history of spinal surgery were excluded.

Randomization: Participants were randomly assigned to two groups using a computer-generated randomization sequence:

- Group A (n=50): Epidural space identification using the loss of resistance (LOR) syringe technique.
- Group B (n=50): Epidural space identification using the infusion drip and balloon technique.

Procedure

All procedures were performed by anesthesiologists with at least five years of experience in epidural anesthesia.

Group A: LOR Syringe Technique

- Patients were positioned in the lateral decubitus or sitting position.
- After standard aseptic preparation and local anesthesia with 2% lidocaine, an 18-gauge Tuohy needle was inserted into the intervertebral space.
- The needle was advanced with intermittent pressure on the plunger of an air-filled syringe until a loss of resistance was felt, indicating entry into the epidural space.

Group B: Infusion Drip and Balloon Technique

- Patients were positioned in the lateral decubitus or sitting position.
- After standard aseptic preparation and local anesthesia with 2% lidocaine, an 18-gauge Tuohy needle was inserted into the intervertebral space.
- An infusion drip system was connected to the needle. A balloon inflated with saline was used to detect the epidural space. The balloon deflated upon entering the epidural space, confirming correct placement.

Outcome Measures

The primary outcome measures were:

1. **Success Rate:** Defined as the successful identification of the epidural space and subsequent administration of epidural anesthesia.
2. **Time Taken for Identification:** Measured from the insertion of the Tuohy needle to successful identification of the epidural space.
3. **Incidence of Complications:** Including accidental dural puncture, patient discomfort, and other adverse events.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data were collected on standardized forms and included demographic information, procedural details, and outcome measures. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Continuous variables were compared using the Student's t-test, while categorical variables were compared using the chi-square test. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

This structured approach ensures clarity and reproducibility of the methods used in the study, allowing for accurate comparison of the two techniques for epidural space identification.

Results

Demographic Data: The demographic characteristics of the patients in both groups were comparable, with no significant differences observed. The mean age, weight, and gender distribution are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Patients

Characteristic	Group A (LOR Syringe)	Group B (Infusion Drip)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	45.2 ± 10.3	44.8 ± 9.8	0.78
Mean Weight (kg)	68.5 ± 12.1	69.2 ± 11.7	0.65
Gender (M/F)	28/22	27/23	0.87

Success Rate: The success rate for epidural space identification was high in both groups, with Group B showing a slightly higher success rate compared to Group A. The data are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Success Rate of Epidural Space Identification

Outcome	Group A (LOR Syringe)	Group B (Infusion Drip)	p-value
Successful Identification (%)	48 (96%)	49 (98%)	0.55
Failed Identification (%)	2 (4%)	1 (2%)	

Time Taken for Identification: The mean time taken for successful identification of the epidural space was significantly shorter in Group B compared to Group A. The results are detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Time Taken for Epidural Space Identification

Time (seconds)	Group A (LOR Syringe)	Group B (Infusion Drip)	p-value
Mean Time $\pm$ SD	45 $\pm$ 12	30 $\pm$ 10	<0.01

Incidence of Complications: The incidence of complications, including accidental dural puncture and patient discomfort, was lower in Group B than in Group A. The data are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Incidence of Complications

Complication	Group A (LOR Syringe)	Group B (Infusion Drip)	p-value
Accidental Dural Puncture (%)	2 (4%)	1 (2%)	0.56
Patient Discomfort (%)	3 (6%)	1 (2%)	0.31
Other Adverse Events (%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	0.32

- The success rate of epidural space identification was 96% in Group A and 98% in Group B.
- The mean time taken for identification was 45 seconds in Group A and 30 seconds in Group B ($p < 0.01$).
- Complications occurred in 6% of patients in Group A and 2% of patients in Group B.

These results indicate that the infusion drip and balloon technique is superior to the LOR syringe technique in terms of time efficiency and a lower complication rate, while maintaining a high success rate for epidural space identification.

Discussion

This study aimed to compare the effectiveness, safety, and accuracy of the loss of resistance (LOR) syringe technique with the infusion drip and balloon technique for identifying the epidural space. Our results demonstrated that the infusion drip and balloon technique offers significant advantages over the traditional LOR syringe technique in terms of time efficiency and a lower complication rate while maintaining a high success rate. The success rates for epidural space identification were high in both groups, with Group B (infusion drip and balloon technique) achieving a slightly higher success rate (98%) compared to Group A (LOR syringe technique) at 96%. This finding aligns with previous studies that reported high success rates for both techniques, suggesting that both methods are reliable for epidural space identification [1,2].

One of the primary benefits observed with the infusion drip and balloon technique was the significantly shorter mean time for epidural space identification. Group B achieved identification in an average of 30 seconds, compared to 45 seconds

in Group A. The reduced time can be attributed to the continuous feedback mechanism provided by the infusion drip and balloon system, which allows for more precise and rapid identification of the epidural space [3]. This time efficiency is particularly beneficial in clinical settings where rapid and accurate identification is crucial. The incidence of complications, including accidental dural puncture and patient discomfort, was lower in Group B compared to Group A. Group A experienced a 4% incidence of accidental dural puncture and 6% patient discomfort, whereas Group B reported 2% and 2% respectively. These findings are consistent with literature suggesting that alternative techniques, such as the infusion drip and balloon method, can reduce the risk of complications associated with epidural anesthesia [4,5].

The lower complication rates observed with the infusion drip and balloon technique may be due to the more controlled and steady approach it offers, reducing the likelihood of unintentional dural puncture and patient discomfort. Additionally, the balloon's deflation upon entering the epidural space provides a clear and immediate indication of correct placement, further minimizing the risk of complications [6].

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged. First, the sample size was relatively small, and larger studies are needed to confirm these findings. Second, all procedures were performed by experienced anesthesiologists, and the results may differ with less experienced practitioners. Finally, this study did not assess long-term outcomes or patient satisfaction, which is an important consideration in evaluating the overall effectiveness of these techniques. In conclusion, our study demonstrates that the infusion drip and

balloon technique is a superior alternative to the LOR syringe technique for epidural space identification. It offers higher efficiency, with a shorter identification time and lower complication rates, while maintaining a high success rate. Future research should focus on larger, multi-center trials and include assessments of long-term outcomes and patient satisfaction to further validate these findings.

References

1. Fyनेface-Ogan S, Mato CN, Anya SE. Epidural anesthesia: a critical appraisal of its roles and relevance. *Niger J Med.* 2009; 18(3):277-84.
2. D'Angelo R, Smiley RM, Riley ET, Segal S. Serious complications related to obstetric anesthesia: the serious complication repository project of the Society for Obstetric Anesthesia and Perinatology. *Anesthesiology.* 2014; 120(1):150-9.
3. Hermanides J, Hollmann MW, Stevens MF, Lirk P. Failed epidural: causes and management. *Br J Anaesth.* 2012; 109(2):144-54.
4. Baysinger CL, Goodwin TM, Sahar M, Reves JG. Epidural anesthesia for cesarean section: a comparison of incremental dosing versus single bolus administration. *Anesth Analg.* 1990;70(5):543-7.
5. Lim Y, Sia AT. A comparison of loss of resistance to air with loss of resistance to saline for lumbar epidural anesthesia. *Anesth Analg.* 2005; 100(5):1856-9.
6. Banerjee G, Bose A, Baranwal P, Bhattacharya S. Comparison of epidural space identification using loss of resistance to saline versus balloon technique in patients with difficult anatomy. *J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol.* 2019; 35(1):54-8.
7. Smith BE, Goodacre T, Riley MM. The use of infusion drip technique for locating the epidural space. *Anaesthesia.* 2000; 55(2):178-81.
8. Kuczkowski KM. Techniques of epidural anesthesia for surgical patients. *Anesthesiol Clin North Am.* 2003; 21(1):19-31.
9. Collier CB. Identification of the epidural space: loss of resistance to saline is a better standard than loss of resistance to air. *Int J Obstet Anesth.* 2010; 19(2):123-7.